

in the check, NCU, SCU, and LCU compared to MBU, PUS, and USG (see table).

With drainage, dry matter yield and N uptake with SCU equaled that with PUS and MBU. LCU and NCU also showed a similar trend. Dry matter yield and N uptake were significantly depressed

with USG, and equaled the dry matter yield and N uptake of the check. Dry matter yield and N uptake of the check were twice what they were with no drainage.

With drainage, the low dry matter yield and N uptake with USG was caused

by cumulative leaching losses of total N (urea + NH_4^+ -N) (see figure). Nitrogen leaching losses were 62.1% for USG, 19.1% for NCU, 16.9% for LCU, 14.3% for PUS, and 13.0% for MBU. No leaching losses of urea or NH_4^+ -N were recorded for SCU.

Effect of micronutrients and farmyard manure on yield and micronutrient content of rice

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A field experiment to determine the effect of micronutrients and farmyard manure (FYM) was conducted on a sodic soil with sand + silt 85.4%, clay 14.6%, CaCO_3 2.45%, pH 10.6, exchangeable sodium percentage 92, CEC 10.0 meq/100 g, gypsum requirement 25 t/ha; and DTPA extractable Fe, Mn, and Zn 3.5, 4.2, and 0.45 ppm, respectively, at Gudha experimental farm of CSSRI.

The experiment was in a split-plot design with 4 replications of 5 micronutrient treatments: T1, control, no micronutrient; T2, 20 ppm Fe; T3, 20 ppm Mn; T4, 5 ppm Zn; and T5, 20 ppm Fe + 20 ppm Mn + 5 ppm Zn and 0 and 10 t FYM/ha. FYM contained 0.85% N, 0.35% P, 0.78% K, 0.35% Ca, 0.24% Mg, 0.22% S, 52 ppm Zn, 125 ppm Mn, 10 ppm Cu, and 320 ppm Fe. Fifty percent of the gypsum requirement was broadcast and mixed and all plots received 150 kg N/ha as urea. Micronutrient sources were $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Plot size was 40m². Micronutrients, FYM, and 75 kg N/ha were broadcast and disced into the soil. Plots

Effect of micronutrients and FYM on rice yield and micronutrient concentration.

Treatment	FYM rate (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha)		Micronutrient concn (ppm)						
		Grain	Straw	Zn			Fe		Mn	
				Leaves	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
Control	0	5.0	8.0	8.5	8.1	10.5	45	335	40	285
	10	5.3	8.3	9.6	9.9	12.8	55	375	48	340
Fe (20 ppm)	0	5.0	8.0	8.4	8.0	10.4	52	360	46	295
	10	5.4	8.4	9.8	10.0	13.1	68	415	52	365
Mn (20 ppm)	0	5.2	8.2	8.6	8.5	10.6	46	340	51	315
	10	5.6	8.7	11.2	11.8	18.2	55	380	58	425
Zn (5 ppm)	0	5.6	8.7	15.5	12.9	25.4	45	340	42	280
	10	6.0	9.1	20.6	15.8	30.5	56	380	48	345
Fe+Mn+Zn	0	6.0	9.1	15.4	12.8	26.8	50	365	55	325
	10	6.0	9.3	21.8	15.1	31.8	68	425	62	480
CD (0.05) for comparing										
FYM level means		0.22	0.35	1.2	0.9	0.7	8	20	6	18
Micronutrient means		0.33	0.44	1.0	0.8	1.6	5	14	3	10

were irrigated and 30-day-old Jaya rice seedlings were transplanted 15 Jul 1979. The remaining 75 kg N was topdressed in 2 equal splits at 3 and 6 weeks of crop growth. Leaf samples of 30-day-old plants (3d and 4th leaves from the top) were collected and plant samples were taken at harvest 1 Nov 1979.

Zn application significantly enhanced the grain and straw yield (see table). Fe and Mn did not affect yield but the highest yield was recorded when these elements were applied with Zn.

Crop growth was poor in plots without Zn and symptoms of moderate

Zn deficiency were noticed at early growth stage (25-30 days). FYM significantly enhanced the yield, irrespective of the micronutrient treatment, possibly because of the increased availability of Zn caused by its application. Zn concentration in 30-day-old leaves was less than the critical 10 ppm value in plots where it was not applied because available soil Zn was less than the critical 0.55 ppm level. Application of Fe, Mn, and Zn enhanced their respective concentration in the crop. FYM also effectively increased micronutrient concentration in the crop.

Comparison of photoperiod-sensitive ratooned rice and normal sown aman rice

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Ratooned and normal sown aman rice varieties were compared. Photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties SR26B, FR13A, Tillakkachari and Achra 108/1 were sown on 14 Nov 1981 and harvested May 1982. Ratooned tillers grew in the fields. A sim-

Comparison of photoperiod-sensitive ratooned and normal sown aman rice, Chinsurah, India, 1981-82.

Variety	Aman sown rice				Ratooned rice			
	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Yield (t/ha)
SR26B	146	22	7	3.7	158	24	11	2.5
FR13A	113	22	8	3.8	146	25	11	3.0
Tillakkachari	142	24	9	3.8	170	26	13	5.0
Achra 108/1	132	25	7	3.9	170	27	11	4.8
Mean	133	23	8	3.7	161	26	12	3.8